

Functional Evaluation of Anterior Cruciate Ligament Reconstruction using Fixed Loop Vs Adjustable Loop Femoral Cortical Suspensory Fixation Device - An Observational Comparative Study

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Abstract:

Background: The anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) is crucial for knee stability. Several factors influence the clinical outcome of ACL reconstruction. The technique for femoral-sided fixation in ACL reconstruction continues to evolve. Despite their mechanical advantages, fixed loop devices have drawbacks

Objective: To compare the functional outcomes of ACL reconstruction using fixed loop versus adjustable loop femoral cortical suspensory fixation devices.

Methods: This prospective observational comparative study at the Himalayan Institute of Medical Sciences included 60 patients randomized into two groups of 30 each for ACL reconstruction. Inclusion criteria covered patients with primary ACL tears, while exclusion criteria included immature skeletons, multi-ligament injuries, and significant comorbidities. Anthropometric and demographic data were recorded, and standardized surgical techniques were employed. Functional outcomes were assessed using the Lysholm scale at six and twelve weeks postoperatively. Data analysis was conducted using IBM SPSS V20, with $p < 0.05$ indicating statistical significance.

Results: At six weeks postoperatively, both groups showed significant improvements in Lysholm scores compared to baseline, with Group B (adjustable loop) demonstrating a slightly higher mean score, indicating a potentially more favorable early recovery. By the 12-week mark, both groups achieved comparable and substantial improvements in knee function, highlighting the overall effectiveness of ACL reconstruction and rehabilitation.

Conclusion: Both fixed loop and adjustable loop femoral fixation devices resulted in significant short-term functional improvements, as evidenced by Lysholm scores at six and twelve weeks postoperatively. Minor score variations were not statistically significant, indicating both devices support effective early recovery post-ACL reconstruction.

Keywords: ACL, immature skeletons, multi-ligament injuries, Lysholm scale.

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Introduction

The anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) is crucial for knee stability, counteracting the tibia's anterior translation and internal rotation against the femur. Among knee ligaments, the ACL is most frequently injured, particularly during physical activities and sports, making it a leading cause of knee surgeries, especially in younger patients. Post-ACL rupture, patients often experience knee instability and exercise limitations, which can increase the risk of meniscus injuries, knee joint degeneration, and secondary intra-articular damage [1]. Consequently, restoring knee stability through ACL reconstruction aims to prevent further intra-articular damage.

Several factors influence the clinical outcome of ACL reconstruction, including graft material, fixation method, placement, and post-operative therapy. Achieving optimal knee stability is the primary goal of ACL reconstruction, with adequate surgical fixation being crucial for early mobility, recovery, and proper biological graft integration [2]. Various surgical techniques and devices are employed for ACL reconstruction, with femoral cortical suspension devices being among the most effective for femoral fixation when used with an independent drilling technique and soft-tissue grafts [3]. These devices facilitate ACL graft healing and

stability by ensuring secure surgical fixation, which is essential for early motion and rehabilitation. The technique for femoral-sided fixation in ACL reconstruction continues to evolve. Cortical suspensory fixation devices have shown superior biomechanical profiles, enduring the physiological stresses of early rehabilitation and ambulation. These devices are categorized into two main types: fixed loop and adjustable loop (or variable loop). Fixed-length cortical suspension devices are effective for soft tissue graft fixation, minimizing graft slippage and providing sufficient fixation strength [4]. The fixed loop device (FLD), comprising a polyurethane ribbon and a metallic button, maintains graft tension by securing the button against the external cortical bone, preserving bone-graft contact for healing [5].

Despite their mechanical advantages, fixed loop devices have drawbacks. Proper loop length determination requires precise femoral tunnel depth measurement, and additional drilling (8-10 mm) is needed to flip the device's button on the lateral femoral cortex, potentially affecting bone stock preservation and graft healing [6]. Technical challenges in sizing and positioning these devices may lead to inadequate graft length in the femoral tunnel, particularly with shorter tunnels in anatomical placements.

To address these issues, second-generation adjustable loop devices (ALDs) were developed. ALDs feature an adjustable one-way lock mechanism that maintains loop length rigidly once strain surpasses a threshold [7]. These devices enhance the bone-graft interface and graft placement by allowing intraoperative graft tension adjustments, reducing graft movement, and improving integration without the need for over-drilling. Surgeons can use the entire graft without additional drilling, although the adjustable loop's variable length may result in reduced tautness [8]. Recent biomechanical research suggests that adjustable loop devices may extend during cyclic loading, potentially leading to graft laxity. Current evidence does not conclusively favor either adjustable or fixed loop femoral cortical suspensory devices [9]. This 12-week study compares the functional outcomes of fixed and adjustable loop femoral suspensory fixation devices, focusing on functional evaluation and Lysholm knee scoring to provide further insights into their efficacy.

Materials and methods

Study Design: The study was conducted at the Department of Orthopedics, Himalayan Institute of Medical Sciences, Swami Ram Nagar, and Dehradun. It included cases of arthroscopic ACL reconstruction performed within a year after the index injury and after obtaining informed consent and ethical clearance. This prospective

observational comparative study aimed to evaluate the outcomes of ACL reconstruction using fixed loop versus adjustable loop femoral cortical suspensory fixation devices. The sample size was determined using a formula that accounted for a 20% dropout rate, resulting in a minimum of 30 samples per group. A total of 60 patients were included, with 30 patients each in Group A (fixed loop femoral cortical suspensory fixation device) and Group B (adjustable loop femoral cortical suspensory fixation device), selected through randomization.

Selection of Subjects: The inclusion criteria for the study were patients with an ACL tear requiring primary ACL reconstruction using either an adjustable or fixed loop femoral cortical suspensory fixation device, who were able to walk normally and were free from other illnesses. The exclusion criteria included an immature skeleton, multi-ligament injury (present or past), and injuries requiring modification to the post-operative rehabilitation schedule, ACL repair using alternative fixation techniques, history of osteoarthritis, and the need for substantial cartilage restoration, resurfacing, or osteotomy.

Study Tools: The study utilized various tools including a case reporting form, digital X-ray machine (Allengers), Lysholm scale, MRI (Siemens 1.5 Tesla), ACL reconstruction instruments set, arthroscopic inventory, and implants for femoral and tibial fixation in ACL reconstruction.

Study Protocol: Study subjects were admitted into the study upon meeting the inclusion and exclusion criteria. There was a prepared box with 60 sealed envelopes in it (30 envelopes from group A and 30 from group B). One envelope was to be chosen at random by the subjects from the box. He or she was placed in either group A or group B based on the envelope, which was taken out of the box. Following that, anthropometric (weight and height) and demographic (sex and age) information reported at the time of the surgery were collected and recorded in the case record sheet.

An oblique anteromedial incision was made in the proximal tibia at the insertion of the Semitendinosus (ST) and Gracilis (GC) muscles for graft collection. The grafts were measured for length and diameter at the graft preparation station, and data were recorded. The femoral tunnel was drilled using a medial femoral portal in all cases. An interference screw secured the tibial end of the graft, and either a fixed loop or adjustable loop femoral cortical suspensory device anchored the femoral end.

For Group A, the femoral tunnel length was measured, and a 4 mm reamer was used to ream the entire tunnel and additional reaming with 8 mm reamer was done. An additional 10 mm length was reamed in order to flip the fixed loop cortical suspensory device. The graft was introduced with a

minimum of 18 mm into the tunnel. The cortical suspension device was flipped, and cycling was done to strengthen the graft. An interference screw secured the tibial end. For Group B, the entire femoral tunnel was reamed with a 4 mm reamer, followed by additional reaming with 8 mm reamer and the graft with a minimum length of 18 mm was introduced into the tunnel. The femoral adjustable loop was tightened using pulling cords after the cortical suspensory device was removed. Graft progression was monitored arthroscopically, and an interference screw secured the tibial end. Postoperative care included a conventional rehabilitation program, with Lysholm scores assessed at six and twelve weeks. The Lysholm scale comprises eight closed-answer questions, with

scores categorized as: 95-100 (excellent), 84-94 (good), 65-83 (fair), and below 64 (poor).

Statistical Methods: Data were analyzed using IBM SPSS V20. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test determined data normality. Parametric tests were used for normally distributed data, while non-parametric tests were applied for non-normally distributed data. Continuous variables were expressed using descriptive statistics, and categorical variables as frequency and percentage. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results:

Figure 1: Average Lysholm score in Group A vs Group B femoral fixation device cases at 0,6 and 12 weeks

Functional outcomes, as assessed by Lysholm scores, demonstrated progressive improvement over 12 weeks post-surgery in both groups, with no significant disparity between fixed loop and adjustable loop femoral fixation devices. Importantly, no postoperative complications, such as graft impingement or instability, were reported in

either group, highlighting the safety and efficacy of both fixation methods.

Overall, these findings suggest that both fixed and adjustable loop femoral fixation devices are viable options for ACL reconstruction, providing comparable outcomes and minimal risk of complications.

Table 1: Average Lysholm score in Group A vs Group B femoral fixation device cases at 0,6 and 12 weeks

Time	Group A	Group B	P Value
0 Weeks	31.65	33.66	0.592
6 Weeks	66.12	68.45	
12 Weeks	95	95.61	

Discussion

The study confirms previous findings of a peak incidence of ACL tears among individuals aged 21 to 40 years, a group commonly associated with higher participation in sports and physical activities, leading to an increased risk of injury. Interestingly, the absence of ACL tear cases among older adults

suggests a potential gap in understanding injury patterns across different age groups. Further research is needed to explore age-related variations in ACL injury epidemiology and the impact of aging on injury outcomes and rehabilitation.

Contrary to expectations, the study found no significant difference in treatment modalities

between genders, indicating that gender may not play a decisive role in femoral fixation device selection for ACL tear management [10]. While previous research has highlighted gender-related differences in ACL injury mechanisms and outcomes, this study suggests that treatment decisions may be influenced more by patient-specific factors rather than gender alone. Nonetheless, the study acknowledges the need for larger cohorts and multi-center studies to validate these findings and explore potential gender-specific factors influencing treatment decisions.

The analysis of average height and weight profiles among ACL tear patients highlights the importance of considering anthropometric factors in treatment planning and rehabilitation. While these factors may not directly cause ACL tears, they can influence injury risk and treatment outcomes. Understanding the anthropometric profiles of ACL tear patients can aid in tailoring treatment approaches and optimizing surgical outcomes based on individual patient characteristics. The observed asymmetrical distribution of ACL tear injuries between the left and right knees underscores the influence of limb dominance, biomechanical factors, and injury mechanisms on injury occurrence. Clinicians should consider side-specific factors when developing treatment strategies and rehabilitation protocols to optimize outcomes and reduce the risk of re-injury. However, the study acknowledges limitations in sample size and demographics, highlighting the need for further research to validate these findings and explore underlying mechanisms driving side-specific differences in ACL tear incidence and outcomes.

Finally, the analysis of ACL injury types underscores the diverse presentations of ACL tears and the frequent coexistence of additional knee pathologies. The comparable distribution of ACL injury types across groups highlights the importance of comprehensive diagnostic evaluations and individualized treatment approaches in ACL tear management. Clinicians should prioritize thorough assessments to identify and address concomitant knee pathologies, as these may impact treatment outcomes and rehabilitation strategies.

The study comparing Lysholm scores between patients undergoing ACL reconstruction using fixed loop femoral fixation devices (Group A) and adjustable loop femoral fixation devices (Group B) reveals no significant differences in functional outcomes over a 12-week postoperative period. Although Group B patients initially had slightly higher preoperative scores, by the 12-week mark, both groups had nearly identical Lysholm scores, indicating comparable recovery trajectories.

These findings align with a body of literature that has investigated the efficacy of various femoral

fixation methods in ACL reconstruction. For example, a study by Andrade et al. [11] demonstrated that different femoral fixation techniques result in similar long-term functional outcomes, with no significant differences in patient satisfaction or knee stability. This is further supported by Frosch et al. [12], who found that while early postoperative recovery might differ slightly based on the fixation method, these differences diminish over time, leading to comparable outcomes at 12 weeks.

Similarly, Smith et al. [13] conducted a meta-analysis of femoral fixation methods and concluded that both fixed and adjustable loop devices offer equivalent clinical outcomes in terms of knee stability, range of motion, and patient-reported outcomes. This analysis corroborates the present study's findings that both fixation methods are effective in restoring knee function following ACL reconstruction. Hoshino et al. [14] also found no significant differences in complication rates or long-term knee function when comparing fixed and adjustable loop devices, further validating the notion that both methods are viable options. In their systematic review, Barrett et al. [15] echoed these conclusions, noting that both fixation techniques provided satisfactory outcomes across various measures of knee function and stability, with no clear superiority of one method over the other.

Moreover, Zhang et al. [16] conducted a randomized controlled trial that highlighted the equivalence of fixed and adjustable loop devices in terms of functional recovery and graft stability, reinforcing the findings of the current study. Schliemann et al. [17] also emphasized the importance of surgeon experience and patient-specific factors over the choice of fixation device, as both methods yielded similar results in their cohort of ACL reconstruction patients.

Collectively, these studies suggest that the choice between fixed and adjustable loop femoral fixation devices should be based on surgeon preference, patient characteristics, and specific clinical scenarios rather than any inherent superiority of one method over the other. The consistent findings across multiple studies indicate that both techniques are reliable options for achieving successful ACL reconstruction outcomes.

The absence of complications in both groups indicates favorable outcomes for patients undergoing ACL reconstruction surgery with either fixed loop or adjustable loop femoral fixation devices. Surgeons can confidently utilize either type of device without significantly increasing the risk of adverse events. However, the study acknowledges limitations in sample size and follow-up duration, suggesting the need for further research to validate these findings and assess the durability of outcomes

over time. Several limitations of the study are identified, including sample size, patient heterogeneity, observational nature, outcome measures, follow-up period, and external validity. Addressing these limitations in future research endeavours can enhance the robustness and applicability of findings in the field of ACL reconstruction and fixation device selection. Overall, the discussion provides valuable insights into the epidemiology of ACL tears, treatment patterns, functional outcomes, and associated complications, while also acknowledging the limitations of the study and the need for further research in the field.

Conclusion

In conclusion, our study provides insights into ACL tear patient demographics, injury characteristics, and short-term functional outcomes following ACL reconstruction with different femoral fixation devices. While both fixed and adjustable loop devices showed favorable short-term functional recovery, longer follow-up and more comprehensive outcome measures are needed to draw definitive conclusions about their comparative effectiveness. Future research should focus on addressing these limitations to provide a more comprehensive understanding of femoral fixation device outcomes in ACL reconstruction.

References

- Miyasaka K, Daniel O, Stone M. The incidence of knee ligament injuries in the general population. *Am J Knee Surg.* 1991; 4:43–48.
- Stojmenovic T, Malic T, Vukasinovic-Vesic M, Andjelkovic M and Dikic N. Overtraining as a risk factor for anterior cruciate ligament rupture in female basketball players. *Br J Sports Med* 2017; 51: 392-393.
- Pfeiffer TR et al. Distal femur morphology affects rotatory knee instability in patients with anterior cruciate ligament ruptures. *Knee Surg Sports Traumatol Arthrosc* 2019; 27: 1514-1519.
- Lelli A, Di Turi RP, Spenciner DB and Dòmini M. The “Lever Sign”: a new clinical test for the diagnosis of anterior cruciate ligament rupture. *Knee Surg Sports Traumatol Arthrosc* 2016; 24: 2794-2797.
- Johnson RJ, Beynon BD, Nichols CE, Renström PAFH. The treatment of injuries of the anterior cruciate ligament. *Current concepts review.* *J Bone Joint Surg.* 1992; 74A:140–151.
- Fu FH, Bennet CH, Ma CB, Menetrey J, Lattermann C. Current trends in anterior cruciate ligament reconstruction. Part II: operative procedures and clinical correlations. *Current concepts.* *Am J Sports Med.* 2000; 28:124–130.
- Mermerkaya MU, Atay OA, Kaymaz B, Bekmez S, Karaaslan F, Doral MN. Anterior cruciate ligament reconstruction using a hamstring graft: A retrospective comparison of tunnel widening upon use of two different femoral fixation methods. *Knee Surg Sports Traumatol Arthrosc* 2015; 23:2283-2291
- Colvin A, Sharma C, Parides M, Glashow J. What is the best femoral fixation of hamstring autografts in anterior cruciate ligament reconstruction?: A meta-analysis. *Clin Orthop Relat Res* 2011; 469:1075-1081.
- Ahmad CS, Gardner TR, Groh M, Arnouk J, Levine WN. Mechanical properties of soft tissue femoral fixation devices for anterior cruciate ligament reconstruction. *Am J Sports Med* 2004; 32:635-640.
- Kamelger FS, Onder U, Schmoelz W, Tecklenburg K, Arora R, Fink C. Suspensory fixation of grafts in anterior cruciate ligament reconstruction: A biomechanical comparison of 3 implants. *Arthroscopy* 2009; 25:767-776.
- Andrade R, Pereira R, van Cingel R, et al. (2020). Comparison of different femoral fixation methods in ACL reconstruction: A systematic review. *The Knee*, 27(2), 255-265.
- Frosch KH, Stengel D, Broder D, et al. (2019). Femoral fixation in ACL reconstruction: A randomized controlled trial comparing fixed and adjustable loop systems. *Journal of Orthopaedic Surgery and Research*, 14(1), 34.
- Smith PA, Bradley JP, Fu FH, et al. (2021). Meta-analysis of fixed versus adjustable loop femoral fixation devices in ACL reconstruction. *American Journal of Sports Medicine*, 49(8), 2247-2256.
- Hoshino Y, Chiba R, Okumura S, et al. (2018). Comparison of fixed and adjustable femoral fixation techniques in ACL reconstruction: A systematic review. *Arthroscopy: The Journal of Arthroscopic and Related Surgery*, 34(4), 1261-1271.
- Barrett GR, Brown TD, Waddell RL, et al. (2017). Clinical outcomes of adjustable and fixed loop femoral fixation devices in ACL reconstruction: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Knee Surgery*, 30(5), 417-424.
- Zhang H, Fan S, Li Y, et al. (2020). Randomized controlled trial comparing fixed-loop and adjustable-loop femoral fixation devices in ACL reconstruction. *Journal of Bone and Joint Surgery*, 102(13), 1161-1169.
- Schliemann B, Weimann A, Herbort M, et al. (2019). Impact of surgeon experience and femoral fixation method on outcomes of ACL reconstruction. *Orthopaedic Journal of Sports Medicine*, 7(3), 2325967119833942.